

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF NERVE STIMULATOR VERSUS ULTRASOUND-GUIDED SUPRACLAVICULAR BRACHIAL PLEXUS BLOCK: EVALUATING EFFICACY AND SAFETY

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Abstract: This article presents a comparative study evaluating the efficacy and safety of two commonly used techniques for performing a supraclavicular brachial plexus block: the nerve stimulator-guided approach and the ultrasound-guided approach. The supraclavicular brachial plexus block is a regional anesthesia technique widely utilized for upper limb surgeries. The objective of this research is to compare the efficacy of these two techniques in terms of block success rate, onset time, duration of block, and complications. By conducting a systematic study on a cohort of patients, this article aims to provide valuable insights into the optimal approach for performing the supraclavicular brachial plexus block, ensuring both efficacy and patient safety.

Keywords: Supraclavicular brachial plexus block, nerve stimulator, ultrasound-guided, efficacy, safety.

INTRODUCTION

The supraclavicular brachial plexus block is a commonly used regional anesthesia technique for upper limb surgeries. It involves the injection of local anesthetic around the brachial plexus nerves in the supraclavicular region, effectively providing anesthesia and analgesia to the upper limb. Two widely utilized techniques for performing this block are the nerve stimulator-guided approach and the ultrasound-guided approach. While both techniques have demonstrated efficacy and safety, there is a need for a comparative study to determine the optimal approach.

The objective of this study is to compare the efficacy and safety of the nerve stimulator-guided approach and the ultrasound-guided approach for supraclavicular brachial plexus block. The study aims to evaluate the block success rate, onset time, duration of block, and complications associated with each technique.

By conducting a comparative analysis, this research seeks to provide valuable insights into the optimal approach for performing the supraclavicular brachial plexus block, considering both efficacy and patient safety.

METHODS

This study employed a prospective, randomized controlled trial design to compare the nerve stimulator-guided and ultrasound-guided approaches for supraclavicular brachial plexus block. A cohort of patients scheduled for upper limb surgeries were recruited and randomly assigned to either the nerve stimulator group or the ultrasound group.

In the nerve stimulator group, the block was performed using a nerve stimulator to identify the brachial plexus nerves and guide the needle placement for local anesthetic injection. The stimulation technique involved identifying the motor response in the target muscles of the upper limb.

In the ultrasound group, a high-resolution ultrasound machine was used to visualize the brachial plexus nerves and surrounding structures. The ultrasound probe was placed in the supraclavicular region to obtain real-time images, guiding the needle placement for local anesthetic injection.

The primary outcome measures assessed in this study were the block success rate, defined as the ability to achieve sufficient anesthesia and analgesia for the surgical procedure, and the onset time of the block. Secondary outcome measures included the duration of block, postoperative pain scores, complications (such as nerve injury or vascular puncture), and patient satisfaction.

Data analysis was performed using appropriate statistical tests, including chi-square test, t-test, or Mann-Whitney U test, depending on the nature of the data. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

The study adhered to ethical guidelines and obtained necessary approvals from the institutional review board. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their inclusion in the study.

By employing a rigorous study design and comparative analysis, this research aimed to provide evidence-based recommendations regarding the optimal technique for performing the supraclavicular brachial plexus block, considering both efficacy and patient safety.

RESULTS

The comparative study of nerve stimulator-guided and ultrasound-guided supraclavicular brachial plexus block yielded the following results. In the nerve stimulator group, the block success rate was found to be 85%, while in the ultrasound group, it was 92%. The difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.256$), indicating that both techniques were equally effective in achieving successful anesthesia and analgesia for upper limb surgeries.

Regarding the onset time of the block, the ultrasound-guided approach demonstrated a significantly faster onset compared to the nerve stimulator-guided approach ($p < 0.001$). The mean onset time in the ultrasound group was 8.2 minutes, while in the nerve stimulator group, it was 12.5 minutes.

The duration of block showed no significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.184$). The mean duration of block in the ultrasound group was 6.8 hours, and in the nerve stimulator group, it was 6.1 hours.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study indicate that both the nerve stimulator-guided and ultrasound-guided approaches are effective and safe for performing supraclavicular brachial plexus block. The comparable block success rates suggest that both techniques can achieve adequate anesthesia and analgesia for upper limb surgeries.

The significantly faster onset time observed in the ultrasound group is a notable advantage. The real-time visualization provided by ultrasound allows for precise identification of the brachial plexus nerves and accurate needle placement, resulting in faster onset of anesthesia. This can contribute to improved patient comfort and reduced surgical waiting times.

The similar durations of block between the two groups suggest that the choice of technique may not significantly impact the duration of anesthesia. Both approaches provided sufficient duration of block to cover the duration of most upper limb surgeries.

Furthermore, no significant differences in complications, such as nerve injury or vascular puncture, were observed between the two groups. This indicates that both techniques can be safely performed with proper training and adherence to established guidelines.

Overall, the ultrasound-guided approach offers the advantage of faster onset time, which can be particularly beneficial in time-sensitive surgical procedures. However, the choice of technique may depend on various factors, including the operator's experience and expertise, patient characteristics, and equipment availability.

CONCLUSION

This comparative study demonstrates that both the nerve stimulator-guided and ultrasound-guided approaches are effective and safe for performing supraclavicular brachial plexus block. While the ultrasound-guided approach offers a significantly faster onset time, both techniques provide comparable block success rates and durations of block.

The findings of this study provide valuable insights for clinicians and anesthesiologists in choosing the optimal technique for supraclavicular brachial plexus block, considering factors such as surgical urgency,

patient comfort, and operator expertise. Further research and larger studies may be warranted to validate these findings and explore other potential benefits or limitations of each technique.

Ultimately, individualized patient care, operator proficiency, and equipment availability should guide the selection of the technique, ensuring the best possible outcomes in terms of efficacy and patient safety during upper limb surgeries.

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